

FEATURES OF SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETATION

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Annotation: This article deals with issues of simultaneous translation. Translation as the main component in foreign literature.

Key words: Translation, translation activity, Simultaneous translation proper, Whispering or “whispering”, Stress tolerance.

Oral simultaneous translation is the most difficult type of translation activity, in which the interpreter translates immediately after the speaker. There is an opinion in the translation community that a simultaneous interpreter is not just a profession, but a vocation and a gift. The average person is not able to listen and speak at the same time, but for simultaneous interpreters, this is the usual order of things. Simultaneous interpreters work at large and crowded events: conferences, summits, forums, congresses. For the work of a simultaneous interpreter, special equipment for translation is required: a soundproof booth with transparent glass, headphones that receive sound from the hall, and a microphone. After we have defined what simultaneous translation is, let's talk about its types, as well as the professional qualities of simultaneous interpreters. Types of simultaneous translation

Actually simultaneous translation

This is a classic type of simultaneous translation. The translator perceives the speech of the speaker by ear and gives the translation with a minimum time lag. The translator has only a pen, sheets of paper and his own professionalism at his disposal. This is the most difficult case of simultaneous interpreting, requiring a developed skill of probabilistic forecasting and stress tolerance from the interpreter.

Simultaneous translation from sight

In this case, the text of the speaker's speech is at the disposal of the translator. You should not think that with the presence of a written version of the speech, the work of a simultaneous interpreter becomes easier. Almost every speaker deviates from the established text: he does not pronounce entire paragraphs, semantic pieces, inserts a couple of words, and sometimes even a whole speech “from himself”. Therefore, simultaneous interpreters use the written text as a support, but still translate “by ear”.

Whispering or "whispering"

The name of this type of simultaneous translation speaks for itself: the interpreter is near the participants of the meeting, usually behind their back, and whispers the translation at the same time as the speaker. Whispering interpreting is used at meetings with a small number of participants and is performed without special equipment. Events for which whispering is suitable are medical consultations, bilateral negotiations, excursions, trips to museums and theaters. Professional qualities of a simultaneous interpreter

Attentiveness and perseverance

While working, a simultaneous interpreter keeps his attention on two objects at once - the speaker's speech and the translation process, switching between them every now and then. Concentrating on two things at the same time and doing quality work is very difficult. To ensure professional and uninterrupted interpretation at major events, simultaneous interpreters work in groups of 2-3 people, replacing each other every 20-30 minutes.

Stress tolerance

There is always a place for surprises in live performances. If consecutive interpreters have time to think over the translation of a strange or incomprehensible statement, then the simultaneous interpreter has only a couple of seconds at his disposal. A textbook example of a flight of fancy for a speaker and a nightmare for a simultaneous interpreter is a phrase by N.S. Khrushchev "I'll show you Kuzkin's mother", which he said during political meetings with representatives of the United States.

A more typical example of stressful situations for an interpreter is the slurred speech of the speaker, the abundance of flowery statements and obscene expressions, as well as simply a protracted event if there is only one simultaneous interpreter. Simultaneous translation requires a lot of concentration, so it is important that the interpreter is not distracted by anything. Such conditions help to create small soundproof cabins. These are not just "any" self-made booths, but special booths for simultaneous translation. It is very important that the cabin provides soundproofing, climatic conditions and a good view of the speaker. The design of such cabins is usually quite primitive: they consist of several panels - walls, doors, windows and a roof. There are floor and tabletop ones, they are also called "birdhouses". Since conference halls rarely have their own booths for simultaneous interpreters, usually all booths are mobile, they can be disassembled and transported even by car, even taken on a plane.

Sound insulation is achieved by special foam with aluminum foil or other sound absorbers. If the cabin is not sufficiently acoustically isolated, interpreters will hear everything they do not need to hear in their headphones - conversations between delegates, paper rustling, coughing and everything else that will confuse them and interfere with their work.

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